

EOSC-ENTRUST Outreach Workshop

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Funded by
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EOSC-ENTRUST Project

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Mission

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to **remove barriers that limit sharing and combining** sensitive data, in a trusted and secure way

- by creating a **European network of trusted research environments** for sensitive data, and
- by joint development of a **common blueprint** for federated data access and analysis to drive European interoperability.

Partners

■ EOSC-ENTRUST partners

[Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputacion](#)

EMBL-EBI

[Sciensano](#)

[University of Essex](#)

[Bielefeld University](#)

[EUDAT Collaborative data infrastructure](#)

[Sigma2 AS](#)

[University of Ljubljana](#)

[BioData.pt](#)

[Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare \(Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos\)](#)

[Stichting Health-RI](#)

[University of Nottingham](#)

[Centre for Genomic Regulation \(CRG\)](#)

[GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften](#)

[SURF](#)

[University of Oslo](#)

[CESSDA ERIC](#)

[GRNET – National Infrastructures for Research and Technology](#)

[Tárki Alapítvány](#)

[University of Tartu](#)

[CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy](#)

[Health Data Research UK \(HDR UK\)](#)

[The University of Manchester](#)

[Uppsala universitet](#)

[Danmarks Tekniske Universitet\(DTU\)](#)

[Luxembourg National Data Service \(LNDS\)](#)

[Turku University of Applied Sciences \(Turun ammattikorkeakoulu\)](#)

[Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie \(VIB\)](#)

[ECRIN \(European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network\)](#)

[Masaryk University](#)

[University of Bergen](#)

[VSB - Technical University of Ostrava](#)

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[NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology](#)

[University of Dundee](#)

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Aligning TRE providers, use cases, and architecture

EOSC-ENTRUST / Open TRE Providers Forum

- Brings together TRE knowledge in a European network of TRE providers
- Both EOSC-ENTRUST and Open forums meet regularly
- Yearly TRE survey as a basis for European TRE provider catalogue to give users insight
- Provides best practices and capabilities to ENTRUST blueprint

Drivers

- 4 **research fields**: genomics, public-private interactions, social science data and clinical trials
- Bring together **TRE requirements** from various real-world use cases and research fields
- Map **user journeys** to give insight in user needs for blueprint development
- Use **real-world use cases** to validate and prototype the Blueprint

Architecture

- Develops Blueprint & Interoperability Framework
- Integrating learnings from all other WPs
- Integrating AAAI and supporting workflow processing
- Defining roles, federation needs & common terminology

Technologies & Workflow processing

- Technologies: develops infrastructure for Authentication, Authorization, Auditing and Accounting
 - TREs use own IAM for identification, connect through common identity in LS-AAI
- Workflow Processing: develops deployable demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows
 - Demonstrator integrating Five Safes TES and Five Safes RO-Crate, aligned with Driver 1 prototype & AAI

Where are we now?

- Second version of **EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint** (+ [training](#)) published, including:
 - 2nd version of architecture specifications
 - SOPs
 - Template legal agreements
 - Governance requirements for a TRE federation
- Second version of [machine-readable TRE providers catalogue](#) published
- EOSC-ENTRUST **Provider Forum & Open Provider Forum** established
- Refined [Driver requirements](#) published
- **Driver prototypes** implementing federated data access developed

Next steps and open questions

- Driver and Provider validation reports of Blueprint v2 published in February
- Final Blueprint next year, Drivers & Providers focus on adoption

Open questions

- **Sustainability:** how can project outputs made sustainable?
 - Open and closed sustainability workshops held in October & November
- **Starting a federation** of TREs (beyond the network)
 - What is feasible? Growth model
 - Federation-readiness of TREs
 - How should a TRE federation connect to the EOSC federation and EHDS?

TREs and data sovereignty

What is data sovereignty?

- The ability of individuals, institutions or states to **retain control** over how data is accessed, processed, shared and reused
- In a European context, a commitment to managing research data **within EU-aligned legal and technical infrastructures** for the benefit of European citizens

Why TREs matter?

- Allowing **cross-institutional and cross-border research** while respecting national data laws
- **Protecting privacy** while allowing high-value research, particularly in health and genomics.
- **Building public trust** by demonstrating that sensitive data is handled responsibly.
- Enabling a “**compute-to-data**” **model** where researchers access data inside controlled environments.
- Providing **auditable, governed access** with clear user authentication and monitoring.

Different stakeholder perspectives

	Stakeholder	Link to data sovereignty	Link to TREs
EOSC	European policy & infrastructure framework	Promotes federated, European-controlled research data infrastructure	Can connect and enable interoperable TREs across Europe
BioMedIT	National secure infrastructure	Keeps sensitive data under Swiss control	Operates national TRE nodes
HDR UK	National health data institute	Develops UK governance model for health data	Leads TRE standards and implementation in the UK
BSC AI Factory	HPC/AI infrastructure	Supports European compute sovereignty	Can host secure compute-to-data environments
Language Data Space	EU Data Space initiative	Governance-based sharing under EU framework	Applies TRE-like controlled access principles

ENTRUST

European Network of Trusted
Research Environments

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